

A Systematic Literature Review of the Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening: Protocol

Authors: Alejandro Jiménez Rios, Sukumar Natarajan, Louise King, Emma Taylor, Zina Abdulla, Richard Ball, Anna Chatzimichali, David Coley, Veronica Ferrandiz-Mas, Robert Grover, Sophia Hatzisavidou, Tristan Kershaw, Murat Mustafa, Brian Rutter, Esha Trivedi, Caroline Watkinson

RENEW

CENTRE FOR REGENERATIVE DESIGN AND
ENGINEERING FOR A NET POSITIVE WORLD

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	I
List of tables	II
List of figures	III
1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) Protocol.....	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Protocol.....	1
References	5
Annex A	6

List of tables

Table 1. Administrative information..... 1
Table 2. Introduction..... 2
Table 3. Methods..... 2
Table 4. History of changes..... 6

List of figures

No table of figures entries found.

1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) Protocol

1.1 Introduction

A transparent systematic review should present completely and accurately why it has been done, what has been done and what was found. The benefits of a systematic review are:

- They allow researchers to identify future research priorities based on the synthesis of state-of-the-art knowledge in a certain field.
- Questions that cannot be addressed by individual studies can be answered by systematic reviews.
- Give a hint to future studies to rectify aspects of primary research identified on them.
- Provide answers to how and why a particular phenomenon occurs based on the generation and/or evaluation of theories.
- They can generate or evaluate theories about how or why phenomena occur.

The PRISMA 2020 [1] methodology, although mainly developed and used in the medical and clinical sciences, could be also applied in engineering and education, as it provides guidance in methodologies to identify, select, appraise and synthesize the available literature. This document presents the protocol adopted to conduct a systematic literature review with the aim of exploring what the effects of indoor greening on occupant health and wellbeing are. It follows the checklist provided by PRISMA and guidelines of the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration [2].

1.2 Protocol

The recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol according to the PRISMA-P methodology [3, 4] are presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Administrative information

• Title:	
• Identification	• A Systematic Literature Review of the Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening: Protocol.
• Update	• Not applicable, this is a new systematic review.
• Registration:	• This protocol has been registered in the OSF Registries website (https://osf.io/registries) under the Generalized Systematic Review Registration Form [5] on 14/12/2025. Its associated project identifier is 8JPQ4 [6] and its corresponding registration number is QFJ48 [7].
• Authors:	
• Contact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alejandro Jiménez Rios <ajr225@bath.ac.uk> • Sukumar Natarajan <sn229@bath.ac.uk> • Louise King <lmk56@bath.ac.uk>; • Emma Taylor <elt58@bath.ac.uk>; • Zina Abdulla <za440@bath.ac.uk>; • Richard Ball <easrjb@bath.ac.uk>; • Anna Chatzimichali <ac3687@bath.ac.uk>; • David Coley <dac33@bath.ac.uk>; • Veronica Ferrandiz-Mas <vfm24@bath.ac.uk>; • Robert Grover <rjg21@bath.ac.uk>; • Sophia Hatzisavvidou <sh2455@bath.ac.uk>; • Tristan Kershaw <tjk28@bath.ac.uk>; • Murat Mustafa <mm3714@bath.ac.uk>; • Brian Rutter <bgr27@bath.ac.uk>; • Esha Trivedi <et969@bath.ac.uk>; • Caroline Watkinson <cw2887@bath.ac.uk>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributions • Amendments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Centre for Regenerative Design & Engineering (RENEW), University of Bath, Bath, United Kingdom • All authors contributed equally to the development of this protocol. • Alejandro Jiménez Rios is the guarantor of the review. • In the event of protocol amendments, the date of each amendment will be accompanied by a description of the change and the rationale. See Annex A.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support: • Sources • Sponsor • Role of sponsor/funder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This project has received funding from the UKRI GREENIN Network (UKRI1239). • The Centre for Regenerative Design & Engineering for a Net Positive World (RENEW) funded this research. • The funder is not involved in any other aspect of the project and will have no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Table 2. Introduction.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rationale: 	<p>People spend up to 90% of their time indoors, making indoor environments critical to human health. Indoor greening—through potted plants, green walls, moss panels, and biophilic design—offers a promising strategy to enhance physical and mental wellbeing. While benefits such as air purification, stress reduction, and improved mood are well-documented, unintended consequences like microbial proliferation, allergen exposure, and maintenance challenges remain underexplored. This review investigates the multifaceted impacts of indoor greening on occupant health and wellbeing, with a focus on mechanisms, outcomes, and future resilience under climate change. The main mechanisms for impact on health and well-being are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air purification: VOC and PM removal via leaf surfaces and root-zone biofiltration • Thermal and humidity regulation: Transpiration effects on comfort • Noise attenuation: Acoustic buffering through foliage • Psychological restoration: Biophilic triggers reducing stress and enhancing mood • Cognitive stimulation: Visual complexity and natural patterns improving attention
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This systematic literature review aims at answering the following main question: • What are the effects of indoor greening on occupant health and wellbeing?

Table 3. Methods.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eligibility criteria: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eligibility criteria will be structured using a modified PICO framework appropriate for environmental exposure research. • Population: Building occupants of any age group in indoor environments, including residential, educational, commercial, and institutional buildings. • Intervention/Exposure: Any form of indoor greening, including indoor plants, green walls, biophilic vegetation installations, and integrated indoor plant systems. • Comparator: Indoor spaces without greening, or different types/intensities of indoor greening interventions (when applicable). • Outcomes: Measures related to physical health (e.g., respiratory function, cardiovascular indicators, indoor air quality exposure outcomes) and mental wellbeing (e.g., stress, mood, perceived wellbeing, cognitive performance). • Study design: Empirical studies including experimental, quasi-experimental, observational, and mixed-methods studies. Reviews, commentaries, and non-empirical works will be excluded.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information sources: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See [8].
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search strategy: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See [8].
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study records: • Data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All retrieved records will be shared in a Teams folder accessible to the review team.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study selection will occur in two stages: (1) title, abstract and keywords screening with two independent groups ranking each record and final inclusion being decided after moderation by a third party, and (2) full-text screening. Reviewers will independently screen all records at each stage

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • • Data collection process 	<p>using predefined eligibility criteria. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion and, if necessary, by consultation with a third reviewer. Reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage will be documented. The screening process will be summarised in a PRISMA flow diagram.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • Data will be extracted independently by reviewers using an Excel data extraction form. Any disagreements will be resolved by discussion or adjudication by a third reviewer. When necessary, reviewers will cross-check data against the original publications for accuracy. No author contacts or external data confirmation methods are planned.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data items: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data to be extracted will include: • Physical Health Indicators/Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Respiratory health: Reduced PM2.5, CO₂, and VOCs ○ Thermal comfort: Improved temperature and humidity regulation ○ Microbial exposure: Potential increase in bioaerosols and allergens ○ Light and circadian rhythm: Influence of plant placement on daylight access • Mental Health Indicators/Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stress reduction: Cortisol level reduction in greened environments ○ Mood enhancement: Positive affect linked to plant presence ○ Cognitive performance: Improved concentration and memory in greened spaces ○ Social connection: Plants as conversation starters and emotional anchors ○ Implications on productivity, reduced absenteeism • Overall Wellbeing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Holistic benefits: Integration of physical, mental, and social health ○ Perceived control and satisfaction: Enhanced agency in personalized green spaces ○ Occupant satisfaction: Higher ratings in green-certified buildings, association with a healthy environment. • Unintended Consequences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Microbial risks: Mold, fungi, and bacteria from overwatering or poor ventilation ○ Potentially increased VOCs ○ Maintenance burden: Stress from upkeep and plant failure ○ Humidity imbalance: Excess moisture affecting building materials ○ Allergen exposure: Pollen and spores in sensitive populations ○ Supply chains/ extractive practices (not sure it is an issue, but I would like to check) • Climate Change Implications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Changing indoor climates: Increased need for passive cooling and humidity control ○ Plant resilience: Species selection under future temperature and light regimes, water vulnerability dependent upon local climate conditions. ○ Health vulnerability: Amplified risks for sensitive groups during heatwaves ○ Monitoring and modelling: Need for adaptive tools to predict greening performance • Regenerative Design Lens <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Beyond sustainability: Designing for net-positive health outcomes ○ Integration with building systems: HVAC, lighting, and water reuse ○ Community wellbeing: Equity in access to indoor nature ○ Feedback loops: Using occupant data to refine greening strategies ○ Nature/ more-than-human wellbeing • Knowledge Gaps and Future Directions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Longitudinal studies: Need for year-round health tracking ○ Standardized metrics: Harmonizing wellbeing indicators ○ Interdisciplinary frameworks: Linking architecture, psychology, and public health ○ Climate-adaptive greening: Predictive modelling under future scenarios • Health Linked Indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Indicator Name (e.g. formaldehyde) ○ Effect of Indoor Greening on Indicator

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gaps or other outcomes 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcomes and prioritization: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The primary outcomes will be: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mental wellbeing indicators including stress reduction, mood changes, perceived wellbeing, affect, and cognitive performance. 2. Physical health indicators such as respiratory symptoms, cardiovascular responses, and physiological stress markers. 3. Indoor environmental quality parameters when directly linked to occupant health (e.g., VOC concentrations, particulate matter, CO₂ levels). • Secondary outcomes include occupant satisfaction, perceived environmental comfort, and aesthetic or psychological benefits not measured physiologically. • Outcomes are prioritised based on relevance to the central research question of health and wellbeing impacts.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of bias in individual studies: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As this is not a meta-analysis and includes design/engineering case studies, formal risk of bias tools will not be used. Instead, the risk of bias and quality of individual studies will be assessed based on the prior experience and background knowledge of the authors of the review working on similar reviews on the past and based on reporting transparency and methodological clarity.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data synthesis: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both a bibliometric analysis and a narrative synthesis will be performed • • The approaches for the bibliometric analysis will be a performance analysis and a science mapping. The performance analysis will be presented in terms of publications per year, most cited authors, most cited records, documents per country, keyword occurrence, and most used source for publication. On the other hand, the science mapping will analyse the co-authorship relationships in terms of authors and countries, as well as the co-occurrence relationships between keywords (both author and index keywords) • • The information of the included records will be qualitatively summarized in a narrative synthesis as the findings are characterized by heterogeneity. The narrative synthesis will be conducted based on thematic analysis. Studies will be grouped by soil type, application method, and retrofitting context
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-bias(es): 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable. No quantitative synthesis is conducted, and publication bias assessment is not feasible in this design-oriented field.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidence in cumulative evidence: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No confidence assessment plan will be used for the proposed systematic review. This is based in the fact that no universally accepted methodology is available for the grading of reviewing in the field. The strength of the body of evidence will be assessed qualitatively by considering breadth, consistency, and methodological transparency.

References

1. Page, M.J., et al., *The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n71. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
2. Page, M.J., et al., *PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n160. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>.
3. Moher, D., et al., *Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015 statement*. Systematic Reviews, 2015. **4**(1): p. 1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-4-1>.
4. Shamseer, L., et al., *Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation*. BMJ : British Medical Journal, 2015. **349**: p. g7647. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g7647>.
5. van den Akker, O.R., et al., *Increasing the transparency of systematic reviews: presenting a generalized registration form*. Systematic Reviews, 2023. **12**(1): p. 170. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02281-7>.
6. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Impacts on Health and Wellbeing Through Indoor Greening: OSF Project*. 2025. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8JPQ4>.
7. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening: Registration*. 2025. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/QFJ48>.
8. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *A Systematic Literature Review of the Impacts on Health and Wellbeing through Indoor Greening: Search Strategy*. 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17928793>.

Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

• Version	• Publication date	• Change
• 1.0	• 17/12/2025	• Initial version.
• 2.0	• 04/02/2026	• The list of data items was expanded.

*This project has received funding from UKRI GREENIN Network
(UKRI1239).*